

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Forensic accounting in predicting the financial performance growth of MTN mobile communication in Nigeria

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Abstract

To emphasize the importance of fraud reporting, fraud prevention, and litigation as forensic accounting instruments, it is necessary to address the issue of financial performance growth in every consistent manner for any company in Nigeria to avoid a collapse in financial performance. The purpose of this paper is to demonstrate how forensic accounting may be used to predict the financial performance and growth of MTN mobile communication in Nigeria in the future.

Methods: The data used for this study was collected from world bank publication, Nigeria stock exchange factbook and National bureau of statistics (NBS) record from a period of 1990 to 2021. The method of data analysis that will be adopted for this paper are ordinary least square (OLS) regression analysis, unit root test, and cointegration analysis. The ordinary least square (OLS) regression model was used in this paper, and the results show that the model is statistically significant, indicating that there is a significant relationship between forensic accounting instruments and growth in financial performance. According to the coefficient of determination (R-squared), forensic accounting indicators can explain approximately 73 per cent of the variation in financial performance growth. This indicates that the fitted model is adequate for predicting the growth of financial performance in the future. A long-term relationship exists between forensic accounting and the financial performance growth of MTN mobile communication in Nigeria, according to the results of the Johansen cointegration test, which was conducted recently. The regression analysis conducted for this paper reveals that the number of fraud cases reported and the rate of fraud prevention, both of which are forensic accounting indicators, are statistically significant and have a positive significant impact on financial performance growth. Furthermore, if fraud is not controlled, it has the potential to devastate the financial performance of telecommunication companies. Therefore, MTN and other telecommunication companies must put in place a policy within their respective organizations that will continuously fund the cost of forensic accounting so that they can maintain a sustainable level of financial performance growth.

Keywords: Financial performance growth; forensic accounting; OLS regression model; R-squared; Johansen cointegration

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1. Introduction

As a result of the increasing prevalence of fraudulent practices in modern organizations, traditional auditing and investigation methods have become inefficient and ineffective in the detection and prevention of the various types of fraud that confront businesses around the world, particularly in Nigeria. Oyejide (2008) said that fraud is a topic that has gotten a great deal of

attention both internationally and in Nigeria, and that this is true. This heightened awareness has been fueled by several high-profile incidents involving a variety of organizations. In the academic literature, issues linked to fraud have also been the subject of careful theoretical and empirical investigation (Appah & Appiah, 2010). The increasing prevalence of fraud, according to Karwai (2002), is causing significant disruption in the Nigerian telecommunications business.